

A Hybrid Method to Predict Network Traffic Demands at a Link Level

Daniel Adanza*, Ricard Vilalta*, Raul Muñoz*, Pol Alemany* and LLuis Gifre*

*Centre Tecnologic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya - CERCA (CTTC-CERCA), Casteldefells, Spain 08860

Email: daniel.adanza@cttc.es

Abstract—Network traffic forecast permits effective resource allocation and allows a more robust thread detection. However, the network infrastructure is more complex than ever in a scenario where the traffic data increases progressively. The introduction of SDN controllers provides more insights on real-time network traffic, and thus traffic forecasting can be easily applied.

This paper presents a hybrid method that has been designed to harness the capabilities of data science, to understand the fluctuations of network traffic; an anomaly detection system, to understand the historically anomalously high traffic demands; and clustering techniques, to identify similar links in the topology. As a main result, a traffic prediction system is created with an enhanced efficiency of 89% in terms of computational overhead, which demonstrates the benefits of implementing different kinds of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in the field of network traffic forecast.

Index Terms—unsupervised machine learning, network traffic forecast, network softwarization

I. INTRODUCTION

Network traffic forecast plays a crucial role since it helps to anticipate and mitigate security threats such as malware, phishing attacks, unauthorized access, and other malicious activities. It allows for performance optimization, identifying bottlenecks and it builds the underpinnings for a more efficient resource allocation.

Unfortunately, effective network traffic prediction is as helpful as challenging. Internet traffic has been rapidly growing at a constant speed since the year 1997 [1] which implies a sheer volume of traffic data generated that can be overwhelming, making it increasingly more difficult to make real-time or near real-time forecasts in a scenario where the network demands more efficient tools and scalable solutions. Additionally, the network infrastructure complexity is higher than ever with an increased need for automation.

The strong interest in the field resulted in a large number of studies that face the forecast challenge from different points of view, such as the integration of random forest to identify the main components that drive network traffic anomalies [2], or the implementation of data science to deeply understand these factors that drive these anomalies in a global scale [3].

Unsupervised Machine Learning (ML) techniques have arisen as a suitable solution, because of their inner way of working. Anomaly Detection Systems (ADS) and clustering techniques can handle large volumes of data efficiently and that makes them scalable whilst being flexible.

They are able to adapt to changing network environments without the need for manual reconfiguration [4]. Some studies already harness these benefits, Y. Liu et al. [5], for instance, aim to benefit the IP network engineering, management and control using a simplistic clustering algorithm. However, it is important to remark the presented method goes one step beyond embedding clustering techniques to enhance the accuracy of the supervised ML algorithms.

Data science also has great potential when enhancing the network traffic forecast. It has the capability of analysing huge amounts of data to identify patterns, trends, and anomalies in network traffic behaviour, and that results in more accurate forecasts [6]. This enables network administrators to make better resource allocation, plan for capacity upgrades, and optimize network performance, ultimately improving efficiency and user experience.

To contribute to the field, a hybrid method is proposed that harnesses the capabilities of data science to understand the normal traffic fluctuations to lately separate the anomaly high traffic demands with the usage of an ADS. Lately, the method integrates data processing and clustering techniques to gain efficiency. Finally, a regressor algorithm will be integrated to forecast the network traffic demands. To the best of our knowledge, there are no other hybrid methods that assemble together all these technologies to create a unique solution with a plausible gain in efficiency.

This paper is structured as follows. Section II presents the current State of the Art (SoA). Section III presents the proposed architecture and the forecasting hybrid method. Section IV presents the experimental evaluation of the proposed method and finally, Section V concludes.

II. THE STATE OF THE ART

Different kinds of AI offer complementary benefits and drawbacks that can be overcome by combining them. For instance, some studies combined an ADS to characterize the normal network traffic behaviour and to detect anomalies, to later implement a regressor and predict the real traffic in the tested environment [7].

Alternatively, other studies propose the usage of clustering techniques to enhance the time series forecast [8] with a demonstrated enhancement in its accuracy that gives them a better understanding of the network characteristics.

The combination of deep learning with supervised ML has also been explored in studies such as [9] where an

enhanced short-term network traffic forecast is suggested by combining convolutional neural networks with more traditional forecasters.

Finally, some studies also opt for a hybrid method where the AI technologies get enhanced with the capabilities of data science, such as [10] where big data and data science techniques are being implemented to extract the main KPI (Key Primary Indicators) to enhance the predictions of the ML algorithms.

An interesting combination between data science and ML can also be found in [11], where the network traffic patterns are being identified in the first instance to classify the access points with the main goal of enhancing the network traffic predictions. However, this method is implemented in a very specific scenario aiming to optimise the resource allocations of the access points specifically for a wireless network.

III. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE AND FORECASTING HYBRID METHOD

This paper implements the TeraFlowSDN architecture which has been presented already in [14] and because of that, the presented paper will only contain a generic description of its architecture.

All in all, the presented TeraFlowSDN splits the main modules of the SDN controller into a number of micro-services, which are designed to target a specific functionality. The chosen container for this architecture is Kubernetes, which is able to carry on a large number of management features.

TeraFlowSDN is designed to cope with scalability and acquire resiliency due to its internal micro-service-based architecture and a meaningful change of the context component. TeraFlowSDN provides network automation and supports multiple workflows instead of just implementing a forecaster.

Hence, the main goal of the presented method would be to enhance the already existing forecaster component by harnessing the capabilities of data science and unsupervised ML techniques which make the forecaster more scalable and efficient.

The proposed hybrid method has been designed and implemented taking into account the following aspects. Firstly, the method integrates data science to understand the main factors that drive traffic fluctuations to build the underpinnings of the forecaster.

Secondly, it implements an ADS to identify abnormally high traffic demands due to unpredictable events to separate the noise from the real facts in the network traffic.

Thirdly, it includes unsupervised ML techniques to identify the most similar links in the network infrastructure to later implement a ML regressor and forecast the network traffic in an efficient and effective manner.

The workflow of the presented method has been illustrated and summarized in Figure 1 where the following inner processes can be found:

- *Data extraction:* Its role consists of extracting useful information and to understand the inner patterns of the

Fig. 1. Workflow of the different processes of the suggested method.

dataset with the main goal of facilitating the ML algorithms to have robust and accurate predictions.

For that purpose, the information (i.e., Raw data) coming from two different sources gets combined: On the one hand, the inner dataset contains different information regarding the characteristics of the link and on the other hand, the input dataset will contain a separate data file containing the traffic demands information including the link's unique identifier, the requested traffic demand for that specific link and a timestamp with the exact time when that traffic demand occurs.

Additionally, the raw data is being processed including new attributes that indicate different features of the link's location and different seasonal information that has been extracted out of the timestamp.

As a main result of this step, a dataset with the following attributes is being generated:

- **Location attributes:** Including the unique link identifier; the source of the link with its corresponding coordinates in the X and Y axis; the destination link with its corresponding coordinates and the geographical distance between the source and the destination. The distance is calculated with three new attributes: the absolute difference in the X-axis, the absolute difference in the Y-axis and the total distance.
- **Seasonal information:** The original timestamps are broken down into six new attributes including the year, the month, the day and the hour included in the requested timestamp (the number of minutes that contains each timestamp is being discarded since it did not seem to help with the predictions of the ML algorithms). Additionally, newly extracted information is also included such as the identified part of the day distinguishing four (morning, afternoon, evening and night) and a boolean acting as a flag identifying the peak times in the traffic demands. For this specific topology, the peak times in traffic demands seem to occur between 13:00 and 15:00 every day.
- **The class attribute:** an integer number measuring the traffic demand for each specific link
- *Clustering:* The main role of this step would be to identify the most similar links in the infrastructure and to be able to classify them depending on their values and the

fluctuations of their traffic demands.

The main idea behind this process is that later on the ML algorithms should only use as train-set the data coming from the links in the same cluster. That can potentially make the prediction process much more efficient without sacrificing accuracy.

For that purpose, the Kmeans algorithm has been implemented with normalized values. To find the optimal number of clusters, the elbow method has been used outputting 8 clusters as an optimal number in this topology. It is worth mentioning, that in this case, the elbow was not very well defined and had to be confirmed by the silhouette coefficients.

For clarification, the results from the elbow method have been included in Figure 3, where it is possible to appreciate that the Sum of Squares Error (SSE) does not present a clear elbow but the curve becomes a bit sharper in the number 8 and 10.

Fig. 2. Error Sum of Squared depending on the number of links used per cluster.

The silhouette coefficients have been included in Figure 2 present however a completely different picture, according to this indicator, to group all the topology in 6 clusters would be the most optimal number. However, it has been decided to use 8 clusters since it presents to be the best option in both indicators and prioritising the SSE.

- *ADS*: The network traffic fluctuations vary greatly due to unlikely and unpredictable events. Abnormally high traffic demands distort statistical metrics and make the ML algorithms have misleading predictions and that is a problem for a method that intends robust and accurate forecasts.

To cope with this issue, an ADS was designed based on the interquartile rule, multiplying by five the interquartile range. The high margin for identifying outliers is justified by the big variability of the class attribute and by the need of not to make a very disruptive ADS.

As a main result, the traffic demands of 266,325 instances

Fig. 3. Silhouette coefficients depending on the number of links used per cluster.

(0.03% of the total dataset) have been identified as abnormally high and because of that, they have been removed from the dataset. . Because of its abnormally high values, these entries distort the statistical metrics and make the ML algorithms have misleading consumptions when using them as train sets.

- *Data Processing*: To optimize the predictions, a data processing step is carried out, incorporating different simplistic actions like attribute conversions, rounding the numeric values to four decimals and eliminating redundant or unimportant information.

As a main result, the dataset is being transformed with optimised values that contain the same information but help the ML algorithm to increase its efficiency in the prediction process.

- *Generate Predictions*: The chosen regressor to predict the traffic demands is the random forest algorithm.

It is important to remark that this algorithm generates the predictions separately and iteratively for each link in the topology, using only as a trainset the processed information coming from the links that are in the same cluster.

To optimize the predictions and enhance its efficiency, the random forest has been configured with 1000 trees and the maximum depth of each tree would be 5. Additionally, the squared error metric has been chosen to measure the quality of a split without any minimum number of samples required to be at a leaf node.

As a main output of this process, the forecasts are being generated and the performance of the ML algorithm is being assessed in terms of accuracy, measuring the relative error rate and efficiency, measuring the total calculation time.

- *An iterative process*: As a final step, the results from the regressor algorithm are being assessed and compared with the real historical values and this generated information will also be included in the dataset for future feedback

TABLE I
SUMMARY RESULTS COMPARING BOTH APPROACHES.

	Relative Error Rate	Calculation Time
Method applied	119.08%	23 s.
Method NOT applied	118.16%	204 s.

and enhancement of its predictions.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The presented work aims to enhance the results of the already existent forecaster with a novel method that harnesses the capabilities of ADS, clustering techniques and data processing.

To do so, the method has been developed in Python version 3.10; the sci-kit library to generate the predictions; pandas and BeautifulSoup for clustering purposes, data extraction and data processing. The ADS has been manually implemented by applying the interquartile rule using the Numpy library.

The suggested approach has been tested by predicting a random sample of 200 links in the infrastructure and comparing two main metrics: the relative error (RE), and the total calculation time.

To assess the method's efficacy, it has been tested using real historical data in a reliable scenario, using the BRAIN research network in Berlin [13], a reasonably big topology with 8993 different links coming from 161 nodes. The input dataset has registered over 2,000,000 traffic demands after taking one-hour samples for 375 days. For each sample, the information regarding the source, destination, the link, the traffic demand and a timestamp with the exact time has been registered.

To quantify the benefits of the suggested method, two different scenarios were created: In the first case, the random forest regressor algorithm with the aforementioned configuration is applied to the input dataset, without making any processes regarding the ADS, data processing and clustering techniques.

In the second case, the suggested method is fully implemented prior to the prediction process. Firstly, the input dataset extracts some features regarding the seasonality and the location of the source and the destination links, secondly, an ADS is being implemented and the instances with abnormally high traffic demand are being removed, thirdly, the data processing step is being carried out and finally, the clustering algorithm divides the data into clusters, so the regressor algorithm will only use as trainsets those links with the instances previously classified in the same cluster which implies that the ML algorithm will only make its predictions based on similar cases which potentially make it more accurate and efficient.

To unbiasedly quantify the benefits of the suggested method, the traffic demands for all the links in the topology have been calculated iteratively in both cases and the average results have been gathered in Table 1.

The presented solution obtained an average relative error rate of 119.08% which is approximately at the same level as the previous approach with 118.16%.

It is important to remark that the class attribute has a very wide range, varying from the minimum, which is 1, to the maximum, which is 56,459,020 for the chosen topology which results in a very high standard deviation of 564,590. The big variability in the class attribute implies a big challenge when predicting the traffic demand patterns and hence it can be expected that the relative error rate would be higher than usual.

Alternatively, Table 1 shows that the solution has proven to be much more efficient reducing meaningfully the calculation time. It predicted the traffic demand of each link with an average of 23 seconds, improving by 88.73% the other approach calculation time.

The strong results in terms of efficiency demonstrate that the suggested method improves the previous approach speed by making it almost 10 times faster. An increase of 0.92% in the RER seems like a minimum price to pay in exchange for the increased speed.

To analyse the performance of the method more thoroughly, the results have also been broken down. Hence, Figure 4, which measures the relative error rate (%) and Figure 5, which shows the total calculation time in seconds for the first six links in the topology.

Fig. 4. The relative error rate average for the first six links in the topology.

Regarding the accuracy results shown in Figure 4 it is worth noticing that the predictions for the traffic demands seem to have a more stable relative error rate when the method is not applied. That is because the regressor algorithm is using as trainset the data from the whole topology. However, the presented method seems to overperform the other approach in the third, fourth and sixth links.

The high inaccuracy in link number five suggests that the method is overperforming the other approach in the majority of the links of the topology but its results are amplified due to the big variability of the class attribute which despite the ADS and the clustering techniques it seems to still make abnormally high traffic demand in some links.

The total calculation time has also been calculated and assessed for both approaches showing a clear advantage for the presented method 5 which presents a much better efficiency in terms of calculation time that can be mostly attributed to the clustering technique which makes the forecaster only use the

Fig. 5. The total calculation time for the first six links in the topology.

top 8 most similar links in the topology but also due to the data processing step. The meaningful gain in efficiency makes also a more stable values taking always between 25 and 37 seconds to generate the predictions for all the instances of each link.

V. CONCLUSION

The implementation of data science, ADS, clustering and ML algorithms are very different technologies with complementary capabilities that when assembled in the right way open the door to new possibilities and can bring benefits that would not be possible otherwise.

It is also worth taking into account that not only the usage of these technologies can lead you to a competitive solution, to harnessing them in the right way and adapting them to each specific scenario can be as challenging as it is rewarding.

The chosen topology presented a big variability of the class attribute which becomes a big challenge to correctly predict the traffic demands. Despite that, the presented method has proven to perform relatively well in terms of accuracy and reducing the calculation time by 89%. This meaningful reduction makes the forecasting process not only more efficient but also more scalable.

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